

Opportunities and Challenges of FAIR Data at Photon and Neutron Facilities

12th–15th October 2025 · Physikzentrum Bad Honnef (PBH), Hauptstraße 5, 53604 Bad Honnef, Germany

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Since 1976, the Physics Center Bad Honnef has served as the discussion and conference venue of the German Physical Society (DPG) in the buildings of the Elly Hölderhoff-Böcking Foundation. The complex originated from a 1902 architectural competition; the winning design, “Letzte Rose” (“Last Rose”) by Berlin architect Gustav Jänicke was realized in 1904–1906. Built in a historicist style with references to the German Renaissance, the ensemble comprises the manor house, a former school building, connecting wings, and a gardener’s lodge; the distinctive western façade and many original interiors are preserved. After being used, among other purposes, as an old people’s home from 1947, the site was developed into a center for scientific exchange.

PBH today serves as the headquarters of the DPG and as an intellectual hub of its scientific life. It provides an environment that fosters in-person encounters, intensive discussion, and collaboration among early-career researchers, established scientists, and international experts—a quality that remains indispensable even in the age of modern communication. The institution’s development is supported by the DPG, the University of Bonn, the Elly Hölderhoff-Böcking Foundation, and the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, embodying the connection between architectural heritage and a vibrant physics community.

Seminar (12–15 October 2025): “Opportunities and Challenges of FAIR Data at Photon and Neutron Facilities.”

Held at PBH in Bad Honnef, this DAPHNE4NFDI seminar brings together researchers working with photon and neutron facilities and/or data to share the current state of the field and to build a common base around FAIR principles, streamlined workflows, and modern data-analysis methods. The programme features overview and introductory lectures, scientific

lectures, data and analysis workflows as well as poster flash talks including poster session sessions to stimulate discussion and networking activities. A special emphasis is on participation by early-career scientists. Conference main chairs are Astrid Schneidewind (FZ Jülich/MLZ), Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt (KIT), and Dirk Lützenkirchen-Hecht (University of Wuppertal); as chairs of the sessions serve additionally Edgar Weckert (DESY), Bridget Murphy (DESY, CAU), Christian Felder (FZJ), Christian Trageser (FZJ), Fabio Dall'Antonia (European XFEL), Frank Weber (KIT), Özgül Öztürk (Uni Siegen), Oliver Knodel (HZDR), Zeynep Isik Dursun (DESY) und Vitaly Biniyaminov (KIT).

- Scientific organizers: Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt, Astrid Schneidewind und Dirk Lützenkirchen-Hecht
- Local organizers: Vitaly Biniyaminov (KIT), Christian Trageser (FZJ) supported on-site by Tim Delrieux (KIT), Oliver Knodel (HZDR)
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ACCESS TO THE EVENT PAGE (incl. material):

<https://events.hifis.net/event/2630/>

Program overview

	12.10.2025 (Sunday)	13.10.2025 (Monday)	14.10.2025 (Tuesday)	15.10.2025 (Wednesday)
8:00	Breakfast			
9:00		Documenting your experiment: The use of electronic notebooks (Wiebke Lohstroh)	Data infrastructures - from a German perspective (York Sure-Vetter)	The need to establish quality and trust in FAIR data (Simon Coles)
9:40		Planning for a batterie data space at HZB (Heike Görzig)	Federating large volumes of data in scientific collaborations (Thorsten Harenberg / Marisa Sandhoff)	Data & analysis from industrial perspective (Simon Jacques / Antony Vamvakeros)
10:20		Coffee	Coffee	Coffee
10:40		ISGN/DataCite (Thorge Peterson)	The science of cooking egg yolk - tracking protein dynamics with big data workflows in DAPHNE4NFDI (Christian Gutt)	Analysis of TOF neutron data (Toby Perring)
11:20		RefXAS database under DAPHNE4NFDI (Abhijeet Gaur)	From Infrastructure to Practice: Empowering Research through Embedded Data Management and Community-Driven Training (Oliver Knodel)	A Digital Twin Workflow for Optimizing X-ray Emission Spectroscopy (XES) Parameters in Materials Science (Cafer Tufan Cakir)
		Asapo - streaming framework for real-time data analysis (Mikhail Karnevskiy)	NFFA-DI: a FAIR-by-design distributed infrastructure (Dario De Angelis)	A glance to a future big data challenge with multibeam ptychography (Mikhail Lyubomirskiy)
	Pydidias - A modular framework for diffraction data analysis: The road towards FAIR software (Malte Storm)	Towards FAIR data workflows at European XFEL with DAMNIT (Fabio Dall'Antonia)	FAIR Data at MLZ - Status and Perspectives (Christian Felder)	
12:20	Lunch & group photo		Lunch	Lunch
14:00	Arrival, Check-In and Welcome coffee	Fair data principles (Gerrit Günther)	Detectors – big data & smart analysis (Max Burian)	Future of FAIR data at photon sources (Britta Redlich)
14:40		Fair data and metadata catalogues (Max Novelli)	Machine Learning for x-ray and neutron science: Concepts, Chances and Challenges (Frank Schreiber)	Future of FAIR Data at Neutron Sources (Helmut Schober)
15:20	Welcome (Astrid Schneidewind, Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt und Dirk Lützenkirchen-Hecht)	Materials spectroscopy: From theoretical approaches and workflows to experimental techniques and their representation in NOMAD (Claudia Draxl)	Soft Matter and Liquid Interfaces X-ray Reflectivity Use Case at Beamline P08 (Nicolas Hayen)	Summary and final Discussion Round presentation of poster prizes
15:30			Metadata schemas for catalysis research at the CatACT beamline (Andrey Sapronov)	
			From Raw Data to Reproducible Insights: Containerized Imaging Analysis for Synchrotron Experiments (Vojtech Kulvait)	
16:00	Considering data at PaN facilities: Challenges and Opportunities (Bridget Murphy)	Coffee	Coffee	Farewell Coffee
16:40	Data on European level - EOSC, and the PaN community contributing to its development (Andy Götz)	Poster flash I	Poster session II	Please note: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The invited talk consists of 30 minutes of presentation and 10 minutes of discussion. The contributed talk consists of 13-min presentation + 5-min discussion. The poster flash consists of 3-min presentation. The conference language will be English.
17:20	Introduction to FAIR data (Mark Wilkinson)	Poster session I		
18:00				
18:30	Dinner	Dinner	Conference Dinner	
20:00	Evening talk: Neuroscience at the intersection of technology and computing (Markus Axer)	Continued poster discussion and interaction		
20:40	Discussions & networking	Discussions & networking	Discussions & networking	

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Program details

Sunday, 12 Oct 2025

Welcome

Speaker: Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt (KIT), Astrid Schneidewind (JCNS/MLZ, FZJ) and Dirk Lützenkirchen-Hecht (BU Wuppertal)

Time: 15:30

Abstract:

Digitalization and data are both a challenge and a powerful asset - central to scientific progress, increasingly prominent through initiatives like DAPHNE4NFDI, NFDI, ERUMData and EOSC, and rapidly evolving with technologies such as LLMs that were barely imaginable just five years ago. We welcome you to the 1st Bad Honnef Seminar: “Opportunities and Challenges of FAIR Data at Photon and Neutron Facilities” which brings together researchers from diverse disciplines to explore the transformative potential of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles in the context of photon and neutron science. Through a series of basic lectures and advanced ones the seminar cover topics like data management strategies, streamlined workflows, and cutting-edge analysis methodologies tailored to synchrotron and neutron data. In addition, lectures will engage with emerging techniques such as on-the-fly analysis and machine learning for data processing and interpretation, while also addressing the pressing challenges of storing and managing the vast volumes of raw, meta, and big data generated by modern facilities. A central theme will be the discussion of the current landscape of FAIR data practices where we stand today and how to improve in data collection and curation. The seminar aims to foster the dialogue among the disciplines and aims to connect early career researchers with established scientists. By bridging disciplines - spanning IT, chemistry, physics, biology, engineering, and mathematics - and institutions including synchrotron and neutron facilities or universities, industry and research institutes, the seminar also looks beyond national borders to align with European and international initiatives. Let us explore new avenues for scientific discovery and innovation, grounded in robust, FAIR data practices.

Considering data at PaN facilities: Challenges and Opportunities

Speaker: Bridget Murphy (invited; DESY, CAU Kiel)

Time: 16:00

Abstract:

In science our data is precious. To use and reuse data, great care must be taken during and after experiments to capture and store not only the data and experimental parameters, but also to record the experiment and analysis workflows. This information is also vital for machine learning analysis applications. Making scientific data FAIR -- Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable is possible due to the increasing digitalization in our society. In this talk I will introduce the basics of best practice and illustrate tools and applications for

high-level, rapid data analysis and discuss the challenge of implementing research data management in real experimental conditions.

I will introduce the DAPHNE4NFDI consortium which brings together users representing key scientific application domains with the large-scale research facilities in photon and neutron science in order to advance the state of data management in the community. Uniquely, DAPHNE4NFDI engages directly with the user community and the large-scale research infrastructure facilities to develop user-driven data solutions to advance science experiments. The main goal of DAPHNE4NFDI is to make data from these experiments "FAIR", thereby making scientific work more efficient and gaining more knowledge from the data. This presentation will give an overview of our activities and elaborate on our progress, showcasing progress in our X-ray reflectivity use-case. Here in addition to electronic laboratory notebooks and persistent sample identifiers, the use case has developed ML-based data analysis. This includes "ML-readiness" of (meta)data, beamline integration, and a reference data collection for ML model training and validation.

Data on European level - EOSC, and the PaN community contributing to its development

Speaker: Andy Götz (invited; ESRF)

Time: 16:40

Abstract:

Data sharing can create new discoveries and verify results published in journals. The more data is can be shared at the European level the more Europe will profit from its investments in science. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a project funded by the European Union to create a research data common for scientific research data in Europe. The talk will explain how EOSC is advancing towards this goal through the recently launched EOSC Federation and the role the Photon and Neutron EOSC Node (PaNOSC) will play. It will explain what PaNOSC offers and how researchers can contribute to and profit from PaNOSC. The talk will end with some thoughts on the issue of data sovereignty in Europe and what it could mean for the future.

Introduction to FAIR data - Is FAIR worthwhile?

Speaker: Mark Wilkinson (invited; Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Time: 17:20

Abstract:

FAIR has the ambition of enabling fully automated discovery and appropriate reuse of scholarly data. The FAIR Principles are promoted by governments, by funding agencies, and by national and international research infrastructures. It is therefore essential to ask: Are there examples where FAIR has fully met its ambitions? Is FAIR making a difference to the research data ecosystem at all? In this presentation, I will strive to provide objective and balanced answers to these questions.

Evening talk: Neuroscience at the intersection of technology and computing

Speaker: Markus Axer (invited; BU Wuppertal, FZJ)

Time: 20:00

Abstract:

The adult human brain contains around 86 billion neurons that are intricately interconnected and organized into functional networks. Decoding the cellular and subcellular details of these networks to reveal their structural and functional properties is a key focus of contemporary brain research. Linking different spatial scales — from synapses (at the nanometer level), to single neurons and glial cells (at the micrometer level), and then to the whole organ — is highly challenging and requires a new culture of large-scale, multidisciplinary collaboration.

In recent years, the European Human Brain Project (HBP) has pioneered the development of the international EBRAINS infrastructure (ebrains.eu), enabling collaborative brain research at the intersection of innovative imaging technologies, big data analytics, and cutting-edge computing resources. This infrastructure was jointly developed by software developers and neuroscientists based on their specific research requirements. EBRAINS provides a wide range of research tools and integrated, curated functional, structural, and metadata, as well as related services, with a focus on human, monkey, rat, and mouse brain atlases. It also enables cloud access to interactive supercomputing, web-based visualization and analysis, and large-scale simulations.

In my presentation, I will introduce the EBRAINS infrastructure and the shared human brain atlas. I will demonstrate a scalable research pipeline for reconstructing neural networks from a series of histological brain sections using polarization microscopy, light scattering and image processing methods based on high-performance computing.

Monday, 13 Oct 2025

Documenting the experimental workflow: the use of electronic lab notebooks and rich metadata annotations

Speaker: Wiebke Lohstroh (invited; TUM)

Time: 09:00

Abstract:

Research data management at Large Scale Facilities (LSFs) plays an important role in the effort to make research data from Neutron and Photon (PaN) research adhere to the FAIR criteria. Experiments at these facilities are typically conducted after successful submission and evaluation of a proposal submitted by a research group, represented by the principle investigator (PI). At all stages of the PaN data life cycle, from sample preparation, experiment conduction and analysis to the publication, the documentation and annotation with metadata is an important part of the work to ensure FAIRness of PaN data. Here, the establishment of fully digital workflows are an important tool, including the use of Electronic laboratory notebooks (ELN) that support the structured collection of metadata. Requirements, challenges and opportunities of ELNs will be discussed as well as the best practices and recommendations for metadata annotations.

Planning for a battery data space at HZB

Speaker: Heike Görzig (invited; HZB)

Time: 09:40

Abstract:

The Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) operates a synchrotron light source BESSY II and has a research focus on energy materials. Within this context, the Institute of Electrochemical Energy Storage (IEES) explores novel battery concepts. The research life-cycle of batteries involves information flows across institute groups and stakeholders. However, the current lack of digitized processes hinders data sharing and reuse. Digitizing metadata and data should optimize the experimental life-cycle by enabling more efficient and effective use of data across various contexts and applications, support advanced analytics, and the use of artificial intelligence.

To address this, the HZB Research Data Management Group (RDM) and the IEES aim to build a battery data space - a conceptual and physical environment for collecting, storing, and sharing data from multiple sources. It will facilitate data accessibility, integration, and analysis across systems, units, and stakeholders. The data space will be developed in close collaboration between scientists of IEES and experts in RDM, using infrastructure to hold data applying commonly agreed principles. This collaboration is driven by the need to establish a trusted and interoperable environment that enables efficient cooperation and ensures the reusability of research outputs beyond individual projects.

Key components of the envisioned infrastructure include components for (meta)data capture, storage and cataloguing in data repositories, and an authentication and

authorization infrastructure, orchestrated by agreed interfaces. Therefore, metadata schemata for general data discovery, as well as domain-specific requirements, play a central role in ensuring data interoperability.

The HZB Battery Data Space will enable federated search, integration into knowledge graphs, and harvesting by federated catalogues set up by initiatives such as EOSC, NFDI, and Helmholtz.

The presentation will provide more details on the motivation and path toward the HZB Battery Data Space.

Tracking Physical Samples with IGSN/DataCite

Speaker: Thorge Peterson (invited; CAU Kiel)

Time: 10:40

Abstract:

The International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) provides globally unique and persistent identifiers for physical samples, enabling traceable connections between samples, research activities, and associated outputs. Through the IGSN–DataCite partnership, IGSN IDs are integrated with DOI infrastructure, supporting interoperability across broader research data ecosystems.

This presentation provides an introduction to the IGSN system, including its purpose, identifier structure, and metadata recommendations. It also shares practical experiences from Kiel University in operating an IGSN registration service, illustrating how IGSNs support FAIR principles for sample management and enhance the findability and reuse of research samples.

RefXAS-database under DAPHNE4NFDI

Speaker: Abhijeet Gaur (contributed; KIT)

Time: 11:00

Abstract:

In the frame of DAPHNE4NFDI, an X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) reference database called RefXAS-database has been set-up where users are provided with well curated XAS reference spectra along with related metadata fields and online processing tools for visualizing the data. The developed online procedure enables users to submit a raw dataset along with its associated metadata via a dedicated website for inclusion in the database. The published data at the database can be easily linked to the raw data available at other repositories. Quality criteria formulated for the uploaded reference data at the database make users aware of the usability of the data. These quality criteria, which are unique to RefXAS-database, are further employed for automatic quality check of the uploaded data which is then followed by manual curation at the interface. Different XAS data formats can be uploaded to RefXAS-database. The output data format consists of all the important

metadata provided during upload including quality criteria, curation details and bibliographic details of the data.

ASAPO - streaming framework for real-time data analysis

Speaker: Mikhail Lyubomirskiy (contributed; Lund University)

Time: 11:20

Abstract:

Modern scientific experiments often generate large amounts of data, creating challenges for real-time processing, analysis, and storage. ASAPO, a high-performance streaming framework developed and deployed at DESY, addresses these challenges by providing a robust solution for establishing data flows.

Leveraging TCP/IP and RDMA over Ethernet and InfiniBand, ASAPO facilitates high-bandwidth communication between detectors, storage systems and analysis processes. It offers user-friendly interfaces for C/C++ and Python on all major platforms, streamlining the development of data-processing pipelines. A high-level Python library simplifies the creation of online data-processing pipelines. Key features include automatic retransfers, trivial parallelization on a per-image basis, support for multi-module detectors, and various monitoring capabilities.

The ASAPO framework, together with supplementary services, is provided as a service across the DESY campus. Several experimental facilities at PETRA III already benefit from ASAPO, employing it to establish data flows. Examples include writing raw and processed data, azimuthal integration of X-ray scattering data, peak finding, and indexing of diffraction patterns. These applications demonstrate ASAPO's versatility and effectiveness in accelerating scientific discovery.

Pydidas - A modular framework for diffraction data analysis: The road towards FAIR software

Speaker: Malte Storm (contributed; hereon)

Time: 11:40

Abstract:

Submitted title: Pydidas - A modular framework for diffraction data analysis: The road towards FAIR software

Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon operates multiple X-ray diffraction (XRD) experiments for external users and while the experiments are very similar, their analysis is not. The variety in data analysis workflows is challenging for creating FAIR analysis workflows because a lot of the analysis is traditionally done with small scripts and not necessarily easily reproducible. Pydidas [1, 2] is a software package developed for the batch analysis of X-ray diffraction data. It is published as open source and intended to be widely reusable. Because the wide range of scientific questions tackled with the technique of XRD, a limited number of generic tools will not be sufficient to allow all possible analysis workflows. Easy extensibility of the

core analysis routines is a key requirement. A framework for creating plugin-based workflows was developed and integrated in the pydidas software package to accommodate different analytical workflows in one software tool.

Plugins are straightforward in their design to allow users/collaborators to extend the standard pydidas plugin library with tailor-made solutions for their analysis requirements. Access to plugins is handled through a registry which automatically finds plugins in specified locations to allow for easy integration of custom plugins. Pydidas also includes (graphical) tools for creating and modifying workflows and for configuring plugins, as well as for running the resulting workflows.

While pydidas was developed with the analysis of X-ray diffraction data in mind and the existing generic analysis plugins reflect this field, the architecture itself is very versatile and can easily be re-used for different research techniques.

[1] <https://pydidas.hereon.de>

[2] <https://github.com/hereon-GEMS/pydidas>

Fair data principles

Speaker: Gerrit Günther (invited; HZB)

Time: 14:00

Abstract:

It can be daunting, considering how to make your data FAIR. In this talk we will use the FAIR data maturity model as a framework for breaking the FAIR principles down into implemental steps. We will highlight concrete actions to improve FAIRness in PaN facilities, and identify the relevant actors to execute them. An overview concludes with practical benefits one gains with implementation, and real-life examples of these.

Fair data and metadata catalogues

Speaker: Max Novelli (invited; ESS)

Time: 14:40

Abstract:

Good scientific metadata requires substantial investments in time, resources, and expertise. To maximize scientific production, it is essential to ensure that data collected can be reused to foster new discoveries within the same field of science, but also across different domains and diverse disciplines. Achieving this goal hinges on adopting the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

This talk will explore the vital role data FAIRness plays in science and beyond, delving into why it is indispensable for unlocking the full potential of data. We will clarify what FAIR data entails, examine the practical steps required to achieve FAIRness, and highlight the distinction between FAIR data and open data. Building on this foundation, we will introduce metadata catalogues which are key tools to facilitate the implementation of FAIR principles, focusing on solutions available in the open-source community. Lastly, we will share insights into the effort and considerations involved in running an open-source metadata catalogue

project that has at its core the FAIR principles.

By embracing FAIR principles and leveraging the power of metadata catalogues, we can unlock new opportunities for collaboration, innovation, and increase the rate of scientific discovery.

Materials spectroscopy: From theoretical approaches and workflows to experimental techniques and their representation in NOMAD

Speaker: Claudia Draxl (invited; HU Berlin, FAIRmat)

Time: 15:20

Abstract:

The incredibly rapid development of modern experimental techniques for investigating materials in labs and spectroscopy facilities is challenging theory to keep up with their pace. Angle-resolved photoemission, optical and x-ray absorption, resonant inelastic x-rays scattering (RIXS), Raman scattering, pump-probe spectroscopies, electron loss spectroscopy, and other techniques provide insight into the structure-property relationship as well as the interplay of electron-electron interaction, electron-vibrational coupling, electron-hole correlation, and exciton-exciton coupling. Elucidating measured data from a theoretical perspective requires the development of advanced methodologies. In this realm, many-body approaches to electronic excitations have become an indispensable tool for gaining profound understanding of all these subtle processes that occur in materials when they are exposed to light. Both advanced experiments and advanced theories require in-depth analysis of the results for their interpretation. Likewise, an extremely detailed description of the underlying data is essential for their later reuse. In this talk, I will present FAIRmat's^[1] approach to describing, processing, analyzing, and storing spectroscopic data from theory and experiments within its data infrastructure NOMAD^[2]. I will also discuss how these data can be repurposed for accelerated materials discovery using artificial intelligence.

[1] <https://fairmat-NFDI.eu>

[2] <https://nomad-lab.eu>

Poster flash (list of pitchers)

1-8: chaired by Özgül Öztürk | 9-17: chaired by Zeynep Isik Dursun

Nr.	Name	Organisation	Pitch Title
01	Fabio Dall'Antonia	EuXFEL	Towards FAIR data workflows at European XFEL with DAMNIT
02	Yuliia Tymoshenko	KIT	Towards FAIR Data at MLZ
03	Otto Lippmann	hereon, CAU Kiel	SciCat metadata Ingestion at P05 Petra Beamline
04	Dmitry Lapkin	Universität Tübingen	Machine Learning for Grazing-Incidence Diffraction (GID): from Raw Data to Crystalline Structure
05	Pieter Glatzel	ESRF	Workflows at the ESRF for spectroscopy
06	Devin Burke	DESY	Bluesky NeXus: Producing NeXus compliant data in Bluesky
07	Carla Terboven	HZB	A Data Steward's Perspective: Supporting Laboratory Scientists with XAS Data Management Workflows at BESSY II
08	Josef Baudisch	MLZ, TUM	MLZ-ELN: Electronic Laboratory Notebook at MLZ
09	Ali Ashtiani	DESY, CAU Kiel	Industry and FAIR: Preparing the Next Generation for Data-Driven Innovation at Photon and Neutron Facilities
10	Adrian Rodriguez-Palomo	Aarhus University	Unraveling the hierarchical structure of narwhal tusk
11	Bishoy Hakim	FAU	Combining Large Scale Facility and Laboratory Data Management within DAPHNE4NFDI
12	Dawit Abiy Hailu	hereon	Pandas for Petra
13	Vojtech	hereon	AMBCAT - Digital Amber Catalogue
14	Athar Khodabakhsh	HZB	Data Preprocessing Challenges in Machine Learning Applications for XAS Studies

15	Rabia Qamar	CAU Kiel	Interaction of Lysozyme with Lipid Monolayers at the Air–Water Interface
16	Sebastian Paripsa	BU Wuppertal	RefXAS – an open access database of X-ray spectra
17	Gergely Farkas	CAS	Diffraction line profile analysis of individual grains in a polycrystal

Tuesday, 14 Oct 2025

Data infrastructures - from a German perspective

Speaker: York Sure-Vetter (invited; NFDI)

Time: 09:00

Abstract:

Submitted title: Making all data FAIR (wait, did he really say "all"?)

Having started in 2020, the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is the new kid on the block. It's a national endeavour which brings together scientific disciplines and scientific data infrastructures from all kinds of scientific disciplines -- including Photon and Neutron facilities. To realize its vision "Data as a common good for excellent research, organised by the scientific community in Germany", NFDI is pushing the use of the FAIR principles for science and is actively shaping the landscape of data services for scientists. As mandated member of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), NFDI is tightly integrated into the European activities. I will give you insights on what it means to build up a new large scale scientific organisation and why IAM is paving the way (please don't worry if you don't know yet what this is ...).

Federating large volumes of data in scientific collaborations

Speaker: Thorsten Harenberg (invited; BU Wuppertal), Marisa Sandhoff (invited; BU Wuppertal)

Time: 09:40

Abstract:

After 15 years of LHC operations, vast experience has been gained in storing and processing unprecedented volumes of data. In this contribution, we present a technical overview of the current state of the art and reflect on the organizational as well as political challenges that have shaped this journey and continue to influence future directions.

The science of cooking egg yolk - tracking protein dynamics with big data workflows in DAPHNE4NFDI

Speaker: Christian Gutt (invited; Universität Siegen)

Time: 10:40

Abstract:

Understanding diffusion and transport in crowded protein solutions is essential for describing biological function, yet quantitative information on force fields, hydrodynamic interactions, and memory effects remains scarce. Existing models are often limited to oversimplified interactions

and require coarse-grained approaches that can incorporate realistic dynamics. Coherent X-ray scattering offers a unique route to probe these processes: using X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy (XPCS), dynamic properties can be inferred directly from temporal fluctuations of scattered intensity. Building a comprehensive, FAIR data bank of protein dynamic X-ray and neutron measurements will be key to advancing theory-experiment integration.

DAPHNE4NFDI provides the digital infrastructure to achieve this. Its tools allow rapid, automated analysis of high-volume dynamic data, real-time experimental control, and efficient data reuse for offline studies. As a case study, I present results on low-density lipoprotein (LDL) particles in egg yolk, including non-equilibrium processes during heating, literally the “science of cooking an egg.” I further discuss machine-learning approaches for de-noising and the first steps toward autonomous XPCS experiments enabled by DAPHNE4NFDI. Altogether, DAPHNE4NFDI exemplifies how integrated data and analysis workflows open new frontiers in quantitative soft-matter and biological physics.

From Infrastructure to Practice: Empowering Research through Embedded Data Management and Community-Driven Training

Speaker: Oliver Knodel (contributed; HZDR)

Time: 11:00

Abstract:

Sustainable research data management (RDM) does not emerge solely from policies or infrastructure — it grows through active engagement, practical integration into research workflows, and a supportive institutional environment. In DAPHNE4NFDI, we aim to strengthen this integration by embedding RDM more deeply into scientific practice at universities and research centers.

Our approach focuses on empowering researchers through tailored training formats, contextualized for the specific needs of photon and neutron science. These activities are co-developed with local stakeholders, ensuring practical relevance and alignment with the actual workflows of scientific users. Rather than offering abstract guidance, we emphasize applied data practices — ranging from metadata creation and storage strategies to the implementation of FAIR principles within real research contexts.

In this talk, we will share experiences and lessons learned from training and support activities, and discuss how institutional structures can be aligned with community needs to foster lasting change. We will also highlight how informal formats — such as hands-on sessions during networking events — can lower barriers and encourage open dialogue around data practices.

Participants are invited to join a follow-up informal mini-session during the networking event, where we will explore lightweight tools and concrete strategies for integrating RDM into

everyday research, and discuss how to build a stronger culture of data stewardship from the bottom up.

NFFA-DI: a FAIR-by-design distributed infrastructure

Speaker: Dario De Angelis (contributed; CNR-ION)

Time: 11:20

Abstract:

In this contribution I will present the NFFA-DI infrastructure, an Italian distributed infrastructure dedicated to nanoscience research activities from sample production and characterization to theoretical modelling. NFFA-DI allows users to access multiple state-of-the-art facilities with a single scientific proposal.

One of the strategic challenges faced by NFFA-DI is the integration of the data management in a digital framework which is compliant to the FAIR principles by construction.

This FAIR-by-design approach involves the upgrade of the laboratories to allow the user collecting data and metadata comprehensively. Digitalization, automation and logbook integration are the main kind of intervention performed on the NFFA-DI laboratories. The entire NFFA-DI data infrastructure (<https://nffa-di.it/en/data-infrastructure/>) is powered with installation of NOMAD Oasis on each institute of the infrastructure.

Towards FAIR data workflows at European XFEL with DAMNIT

Speaker: Fabio Dall'Antonia (invited; European XFEL)

Time: 11:40

Abstract:

We present the current state of the DAMNIT software which is a framework that extracts and visualises data and metadata from several stages of the scientific data lifecycle, starting with the primary experiment data sources and adding information from triggered analysis software later on.

The main motivation for DAMNIT development lies in the complexity of European XFEL data, with respect to both the experiment-diagnostic data "near online" and the downstream, reduced data - all of which are presented through a local application GUI and lately also in a beta-phase web frontend, some details of which are shared.

DAMNIT is controlled by high-level Python code which can be used to describe workflows, including the embedding of one or more data processing pipelines. In that context we present our plans to further develop DAMNIT, with a focus on interoperability and reusability of processing workflows through software provenance in metadata. Such information can be used to feed metadata catalogues and specifically produced NeXus files.

Detectors – big data & smart analysis - Operationalizing FAIR Workflows Across Large-Scale Research

Speaker: Max Burian (invited; DECTRIS)

Time: 14:00

Abstract:

FAIR principles apply to workflows as well as data. This talk presents a reference architecture for FAIR-compliant analysis pipelines for STEM sciences, particularly experiments with large data volumes. The approach combines (i) composable, versioned workflow templates, (ii) portable, community-maintained execution environments, (iii) automated, standards-based provenance with persistent identifiers for data, software, and runs, including an outlook into future developments such as policy-aware orchestration on HPC and commercial clouds. I discuss federation across facilities (identity, authorization, cost attribution, stewardship) and report operational metrics toward reproducible, comparable, and reusable workflows.

Machine Learning for x-ray and neutron science: Concepts, Chances and Challenges

Speaker: Frank Schreiber (invited; Universität Tübingen)

Time: 14:40

Abstract:

X-ray and neutron scattering are indispensable tools. Modern sources enable even time-resolved experiments, producing large data sets in short time. Machine learning (ML) techniques offer a data filtering and analysis strategy complementary to conventional approaches, including even experimental control and optimization.

We first provide a brief overview of the concepts of ML applied to scattering and explain some of the requirements for its successful application.

Second, as a specific use case to illustrate the chances and challenges, we discuss surface scattering, starting with a summary of different surface scattering geometries (reflectometry (NR/XRR); grazing-incidence wide / small angle scattering (GISANS/GISAXS/GIWAXS)). We discuss our ML solution for NR/XRR and explain why this seemingly simple, essentially one-dimensional problem is actually more difficult, and why some other approaches have failed. We present our most recent solutions for NR/XRR [5,9], including the “normalizing flows” strategy for the incorporation of distributions of parameters for the solution, which allows to quantify error bars.

Third, we present our ML strategy for grazing-incidence scattering data, including the specifics of the geometry with distortions of the data, which can be challenging for ML-based feature recognition.

Fourth, we outline our efforts for ML data analysis pipelines employable at public instruments, including closed-loop experimental control with feedback of the ML-based analysis for the experiment.

Last, we point out the role of big-data projects such as DAPHNE4NFDI, data base projects such as <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6497437> (Reflectometry Curves (XRR and NR) and Corresponding Fits for Machine Learning) and other joint efforts of the community.

Soft Matter and Liquid Interfaces X-ray Reflectivity Use Case at Beamline P08 & Tracking Physical Samples with IGSN: X-Ray Reflectivity Use Case

Speaker: Nicolas Hayen (contributed; CAU Kiel)

Time: 15:20

Abstract:

FAIR data workflows and tools established in DAPHNE4NFDI are applied at beamline P08, PETRA III, DESY, as part of the X-ray reflectivity use case UC6, with the ultimate goal of demonstrating fully FAIR research data management in a synchrotron beamline environment. In close collaboration with DESY beamline scientists, experimental control, and IT, metadata is automatically aggregated according to the proposed DAPHNE4NFDI schema^[1] and ingested into electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs)^[2] and the SciCat metadata catalogue. Persistent identifiers like Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and International Generic Sample Numbers (IGSNs) are used to uniquely identify resources. Additionally, we will discuss the integration of a Reference Database for Photon and Neutron (PaN) reflectivity data [3, 4], as well as the application of advanced machine learning solutions^[5, 6, 7] for real-time and offline analysis of PaN reflectometry data. This talk will highlight the new developments in each of these areas in the context of a FAIR research data lifecycle and outline upcoming improvements to tools provided by DAPHNE4NFDI.

References

- [1] W. Lohstroh et al., DAPHNE4NFDI - Draft recommendations on metadata capture and specifications (1.0). Zenodo (2024)
- [2] P. Jordt et. al., Supplementary Information for Publication: Specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) in the Photon and Neutron Community. Zenodo (2025)
- [3] <https://public-data.desy.de>
- [4] <https://sisyphos.desy.de>
- [5] A. Greco et al., *J. Appl. Cryst.* **55**, 362-369 (2022).
- [6] V. Munteanu et al., *J. Appl. Cryst.* **57**, 456-469 (2024).
- [7] V. Starostin et. al., *Sci. Adv.* **11**, eadr9668 (2025).

Metadata schemas for catalysis research at the CatAct beamline

Speaker: Andrey Sapronov (contributed; KIT)

Time: 15:40

Abstract:

Aiming towards an automated operando catalysis experiment at the CATACT beamline, we are integrating a set of RDM services, such as sample catalogs, data catalogs, and electronic laboratory notebooks (ELN). The CATACT beamline hosts all necessary instrumentation coupled with personnel expertise to perform heterogeneous catalyst characterization and testing. This hardware setup is expected to be complemented by such software services as Sepia for sample information management, SciCat as a scientific data catalog, and Adacta and Kadi4Mat for devices and measurement administration. The accompanying metadata must be extensively described using established LinkML schemas.

Wednesday, 15 Oct 2025

The need to establish quality and trust in FAIR data

Speaker: Simon Coles (invited; University Southampton)

Time: 09:00

Abstract:

Coordinated national and international approaches to data management

The UK Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI, <https://www.psdi.ac.uk/>) aims to grow trustworthy data collections and link together data infrastructures that researchers already use. It is therefore a set of data resources, tools and services that act as a platform to empower researchers. PSDI has been operational for 6 months and this talk will showcase a range of resources and outline projects that build on them e.g. an AI for Science project building data pipelines using machine learning methods to underpin serial and materials crystallography at Diamond Light Source.

The talk will also outline efforts at an international level to coordinate approaches to raw diffraction data management through the auspices of its Committee on Data (CommDat, <https://www.iucr.org/resources/data/commdat>). The most notable recent activity is the launch of a new journal, Raw Data Letters, aimed at surfacing raw diffraction data of interest to the wider community with a view to solving tough problems, for training, and to develop data processing software.

Data & analysis from industrial perspective

Speaker: Simon Jacques (invited; FINDEN), Antony Vamvakeros (invited; FINDEN)

Time: 09:40

Abstract:

Finden Ltd is a UK micro-SME scientific service provider working with multinational clients in the energy, chemicals, pharmaceutical and automotive sectors. We frequently run time-critical imaging experiments at synchrotrons and in the lab. The resulting X-ray CT datasets, ranging from conventional micro and nano X-ray-CT to XRD-CT are large, chemically rich (XRD-CT) and often affected by wide range of artefacts such as noise, parallax, angular undersampling and photon starvation, which must be handled quickly to meet strict deadlines. I will present machine learning methods we have developed over the past five years for denoising, artefact correction (including parallax mitigation), segmentation, super-resolution and tomographic reconstruction. Examples will use only our peer-reviewed technical work (e.g. nDTomo, DLSR, PQ-Net, SD2I, ParallaxNet, SAMBA) as well as the new Battery Imaging Library which is the first open access multi-modal and multi-length scale battery imaging library (<https://www.batteryimaginglibrary.com/>).

Analysis of time-of-flight neutron data

Speaker: Toby Perring (invited; ISIS)

Time: 10:40

Abstract:

Data interpretation and management at a user facility poses a variety of challenges, but at neutron sources these are exacerbated by the size of the data sets produced by time-of-flight instruments – be they at the intrinsically pulsed spallation sources, or at reactor sources.

This talk will describe data analysis workflows for time-of-flight neutron data analysis and will illustrate them with a few characteristic experiments across the broad scientific programme at conducted at any neutron facility. This is to highlight some of the techniques that have been opened up by time-of-flight techniques, and also some bottlenecks of performing the data analysis. Present and future challenges as well as opportunities for facilities will be discussed, together with the value of standards and FAIR principles in handling with them.

A Digital Twin Workflow for Optimizing X-ray Emission Spectroscopy (XES) Parameters in Materials Science

Speaker: Cafce Tufan Cakir (invited; BAM)

Time: 11:00

Abstract:

We present a digital twin-based workflow designed to optimize experimental parameters in X-ray emission spectroscopy (XES), with a focus on reproducibility, data integration, and alignment with FAIR principles in materials science and engineering.

The developed pipeline begins with automated retrieval of crystallographic information from the Materials Project database based on a given sample composition. This structural data is then used to simulate the corresponding XES spectra using FDMNES, allowing for accurate prediction of element-specific emission lines.

The simulated emission lines are fed into an X-ray tracing (XRT) module, which builds a virtual replica of the experimental setup. This digital twin environment enables predictive modeling of spectrometer performance based on geometric configurations. The optimization focuses on two key parameters: the choice of the analyzing crystal and the distance between the sample and crystal (which also defines the crystal–detector distance due to Bragg condition constraints). An active learning algorithm is employed to iteratively adjust these parameters in order to achieve a desired energy-per-pixel (E/pixel) resolution with minimal intensity loss, enabling efficient, data-driven experimental planning.

By integrating data-driven simulations with real-time optimization strategies, this workflow supports efficient experiment planning while minimizing resource consumption and human error. Furthermore, all stages of the process—from data collection and simulation to optimization and visualization—are structured to ensure traceability and interoperability, facilitating future reuse and collaborative research.

A glance to a future big data challenge with multibeam ptychography

Speaker: Mikhail Lyubomirskyi (contributed; Lund University)

Time: 11:20

Abstract:

Currently, X-ray imaging is taking over the leading position of data generators at synchrotrons. The method called X-ray ptychography has the highest documented resolution among other imaging methods. However, the amount of raw data required for generating a single sample projection can become a bottleneck for most ambitious experiments, especially for 3D and/or functional studies, not only due to data size. So far, the acquisition speed in X-ray ptychography has been limited by the available coherent flux provided by modern synchrotrons, such as PETRA III. Parallel data acquisition in the next step of development of ptychography, called multibeam ptychography, has overcome this limitation, but it generates even larger data volumes at current synchrotrons. FAIR data policy will likely face unexpected challenges in the near future as fourth-generation synchrotrons come into full operation. However, we can already gain insight into these challenges today through quick acquisition ptychography.

FAIR Data at MLZ - Status and Perspectives

Speaker: Christian Felder (contributed; JCNS/MLZ)

Time: 11:40

Abstract:

Data management at the Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (MLZ) has seen substantial advancements in recent years, particularly during our reactor downtime. This talk will provide an overview of the implementation of FAIR data at the MLZ. Through a live demonstration using a virtual instrument, the presentation will guide the audience through the process of performing an experiment. This includes seamlessly capturing metadata during the measurement, taking electronic lab notes in a collaborative web app, accessing web-based data analysis tools at the MLZ, and downloading data.

Future of FAIR Data at Photon Sources

Speaker: Britta Redlich (invited; DESY)

Time: 14:00

Abstract:

Photon science has entered an era where the scale and complexity of data produced by modern facilities necessitates a paradigm shift in data management. This talk will outline DESY's vision for data stewardship at next-generation facilities such as PETRA IV, where we anticipate exponential growth in data volumes. This trend is already evident at current facilities, driven by increased automation and large-area high-speed detectors. To manage this data, central data management, remote access and user-centric services will be essential in which the DAPHNE4NFDI consortium has an important role to play. At DESY, and within the League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources (LEAPS), efforts are well underway to implement FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles across the full data lifecycle from proposal to publication. These developments and deployment of data catalogues such as SciCat and the integration of persistent identifiers (DOI, IGSN) illustrate how FAIR concepts are being operationalised. The presentation will also discuss collaborations within LEAPS and with other large-scale research networks such as LENS to establish interoperable data infrastructures and trusted repositories, paving the way for a federated European data ecosystem that supports open, high-quality and AI-ready photon science.

Future of FAIR Data at Neutron Sources

Speaker: Helmut Schober (invited; ESS)

Time: 14:40

Abstract:

From Observations to Impact: The Role of Data Guiding the Scientific Discovery Journey

The European Spallation Source (ESS) is poised to become a global leader in neutron science, driving transformative advancements across diverse scientific domains while continuously pushing the boundaries of technical innovation. At the beginning of the presentation, I will provide a brief overview of how ESS operates, our current status with the project, and the long-term vision for what we must achieve.

Central to realizing ESS's ambitious vision is the effective utilization and management of scientific data. While the sheer volume of data generated by ESS experiments is not the main challenge, the critical task lies in empowering the diverse community of researchers using our facilities to effectively extract the insights they need to produce meaningful and impactful scientific outcomes.

To address this challenge, ESS, in collaboration with the broader neutron science community, must establish a robust ecosystem of tools and methodologies that bridge the gap between raw experimental data and actionable results. A cornerstone of this effort is our commitment to adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, which aim to maximize the accessibility and utility of scientific output. However, implementing FAIR practices is a complex, multifaceted endeavor that must take into account the diversity in research goals, workflows, and data requirements.

This presentation will elaborate on how ESS approaches the many facets of this endeavor, with particular focus on the need to define and clearly characterize the various data categories involved - ranging from raw experimental output to highly processed insights. These categories play a critical role in enabling the transformation of observations into actionable knowledge and know-how. It is through thoughtful frameworks and tailored solutions, that we hope to ensure that bold scientific ideas translate into impactful discoveries that advance both science and society.

Abstracts of poster pitches:

Towards FAIR data workflows at European XFEL with DAMNIT

Speaker: Fabio Dall'Antonia (contributed; European XFEL)

Abstract:

We present the current state of the DAMNIT software which is a framework that extracts and visualises data and metadata from several stages of the scientific data lifecycle, starting with the primary experiment data sources and adding information from triggered analysis software later on.

The main motivation for DAMNIT development lies in the complexity of European XFEL data, with respect to both the experiment-diagnostic data "near online" and the downstream, reduced data — all of which are presented through a local application GUI and lately also in a beta-phase web frontend, some details of which are shared.

DAMNIT is controlled by high-level Python code which can be used to describe workflows, including the embedding of one or more data processing pipelines. In that context we present our plans to further develop DAMNIT, with a focus on interoperability and reusability of processing workflows through software provenance in metadata. Such information can be used to feed metadata catalogues and specifically produced NeXus files.

Towards FAIR Data at MLZ

Speaker: Yuliia Tymoshenko (contributed; KIT)

Abstract:

DAPHNE4NFDI is a consortium within the Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) in Germany, dedicated to developing data management tools and best practices for research data from Photon and Neutron (PaN) sources. The consortium's tasks include collecting and documenting data and metadata during experiments with the aim of enhancing the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) of data. Here, we present draft recommendations for the capture, aggregation, and storage of metadata for experiments at PaN large-scale infrastructure facilities, as well as an electronic laboratory notebook that we are developing and setting up for MLZ users.

SciCat metadata Ingestion at P05 Petra Beamline

Speaker: Otto Lippmann (contributed; hereon, CAU Kiel)

Abstract:

This poster presents the implementation of metadata ingestion in the Scicat catalog at the P05 image beamline at DESY, operated by Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon. Following the DAPHNE4NFDI standards, we have established a workflow to populate the metadata catalog with datasets

generated over recent years and to automate ingestion for future experiments. The system integrates two software components: one responsible for creating a Scicat entry upon beamtime release, incorporating administrative data from the Door proposal system such as proposal ID and responsible personnel. The second script manages the upload of scientific metadata post-experiment, linking it to the generated dataset. This script also facilitates the integration of legacy data into the catalog. Looking ahead, we plan to automate the inclusion of scientific metadata alongside proposal information. This presentation will detail the current status of our implementation, provide insights into project outlook, and highlight adherence to DAIR data principles.

Machine Learning for Grazing-Incidence Diffraction (GID): from Raw Data to Crystalline Structure

Speaker: Dmitry Lapkin (contributed; Universität Tübingen)

Abstract:

Novel materials in the form of thin films are widely used in modern industrial applications, including coatings, microelectronics, photovoltaics, etc. The optimization of such materials for specific applications requires the appropriate structural characterization methods. X-ray and neutron scattering techniques, such as grazing incidence small- and wide-angle X-ray/neutron scattering (GISAXS/GIWAXS/GISANS) or grazing-incidence diffraction (GID), provide ultimate spatial resolution and high surface sensitivity, making them indispensable tools for thin film studies. At the same time, advancements in X-ray and neutron sources, in conjunction with developments in area detector technologies, enable the recording of several terabytes of raw two-dimensional detector data within a single experiment. Conventional methods of analysing the GID data are severely under-paced compared to the data generation rates, representing a significant bottleneck, and leaving much of the measured data unanalysed. To make the thin film studies more efficient and increase the amount of analysed and published GID data that can be reused, we are developing machine learning approaches for handling such data. Our ultimate goal is to create a complete data analysis pipeline that goes from raw detector patterns to the corresponding crystalline structures. This pipeline comprises several stages, including data preprocessing and reduction, Bragg peak identification and refinement, and crystal structure determination. We are also developing a data format that will connect all these data analysis stages and include comprehensive experimental and sample metadata, in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Workflows at the ESRF for spectroscopy

Speaker: Pieter Glatzel (contributed; ESRF)

Abstract:

Adding photon-out spectroscopy instrumentation to an X-ray absorption beamline requires additional tools for data acquisition and reduction, and adaptation of definitions for data deposition. We are developing at the ESRF together with the collaborating beamlines protocols

and software that address the needs that arise with photon-out spectroscopy. The tools are embedded in general software packages for X-ray absorption spectroscopy. In order to ensure FAIR data, all steps of data treatment starting from raw data must be traceable.

Bluesky NeXus: Producing NeXus-compliant data in Bluesky

Speaker: Devin Burke (contributed; DESY)

Abstract:

We present a tool to automate the compilation, validation, and serialization of a NeXus-compliant data structure using the Bluesky control system and Pydantic. Bluesky NeXus is a tool and strategy that leverages Pydantic to build and validate NeXus-compliant objects which are attached as metadata to experimental devices. Bluesky, as the experiment orchestrator, can then compile this metadata and serialize a compliant structure into its data stream, making analysis and data ingestion easier for downstream consumers.

A Data Steward's Perspective: Supporting Laboratory Scientists with XAS Data Management Workflows at BESSY II

Speaker: Carla Terboven (contributed; HZB)

Abstract:

This contribution reflects the perspective of a data steward accompanying a group of laboratory scientists to a synchrotron beamline for X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) experiments. A six-step data pipeline is introduced, spanning from laboratory sample history and SampleID assignment to data upload, lightweight parsing, rapid quality checks via automated plots, and advanced comparative analysis across multiple beamtimes. The pipeline emphasizes usability and flexibility, enabling immediate benefits such as quick assessment of measurement quality, integration with reference data, and filtering by edge or element. In the long term, it facilitates consistent reuse and deeper analysis by linking beamline data with the full experimental context. The approach uses NOMAD for data storage and leverages a lightweight parsing strategy tailored to the needs of laboratory scientists—focusing less on metadata completeness and more on practical utility and researcher-driven workflows. This case study discusses how FAIR data principles can be implemented in a way that is both efficient and aligned with everyday experimental practice.

MLZ-ELN: Electronic Laboratory Notebook at MLZ

Speaker: Josef Baudisch (contributed; MLZ, TUM)

Abstract:

The MLZ has enhanced its digital infrastructure with seamless metadata capture via NICOS and centralized data access through SciCat. A Single Sign-On system simplifies user access. The MLZ-ELN, fully containerized and integrated with MLZ systems, has been running continuously since July 2024, supporting efficient, facility-wide digital workflows.

Industry and FAIR: Preparing the Next Generation for Data-Driven Innovation at Photon and Neutron Facilities

Speaker: Ali Ashtiani (contributed; CAU Kiel)

Abstract:

As FAIR data principles become embedded in the operations of research infrastructures (RIs), their relevance reaches well beyond academia. This is especially true for the next generation of scientists and engineers who will work in environments where FAIR-aligned practices are expected across both public and industrial research. This contribution shares insights from a recent white paper focused on three key industry stakeholder groups within the photon and neutron (PaN) ecosystem: private funders of research projects, industrial users conducting experiments at large-scale facilities, and third-party users of open FAIR data. These actors bring specific requirements and constraints—from secure, permission-based access and machine-actionable metadata to scalable data infrastructures.

By highlighting common challenges and strategic opportunities for these groups, we argue that early-career researchers can enhance their career readiness by mastering FAIR workflows, metadata standards, and data-stewardship tools. In a future where FAIR principles are standard practice across research and industry, equipping young scientists with this knowledge is essential. The talk invites reflection on how research data management training, facility support services, and open-science policies can empower the upcoming generation to lead in a data-intensive, FAIR-enabled research landscape.

Unraveling the hierarchical structure of narwhal tusk

Speaker: Adrian Rodriguez-Palomo (contributed; Aarhus University)

Abstract:

Narwhals are fascinating marine mammals, renowned for their left-handed spiral tusk, which has captivated human imagination for centuries and is linked to the unicorn myth. This twisted structure, primarily found in males, exhibits highly anisotropic mechanical properties and remarkable impact resistance. We hypothesize that the orientation of the biological nanostructure mirrors the tusk's spiral macro-structure, which ultimately defines its mechanical characteristics. We employed a multi-scale approach using 2D and 3D X-ray and polarized visible light imaging to investigate this. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), X-ray diffraction imaging (XRD), X-ray fluorescence, and birefringence microscopy were utilized to analyze the anisotropy of the tusk's fundamental building blocks (mineralized collagen fibrils) across different hierarchical levels. Structurally, the narwhal tusk consists of a central pulp chamber encased by primary dentine and an outer cementum layer. Unlike human teeth, it lacks enamel. While its fundamental components are similar to other mineralized tissues, the degree of anisotropy and spatial distribution diverge significantly from, for instance, bone. SAXS tensor tomography revealed pronounced anisotropy in the dentine, with mineralized collagen fibrils aligned longitudinally. Notably, we observed a gradual twist in the fiber orientation, increasing radially

to form a helical pattern extending from the pulp chamber to the cementum. The cementum layer, covering the tusk's exterior, exhibited a distinct structure with radially oriented domains embedded in a predominantly longitudinal matrix. At the nanoscale, the periodicity of collagen fibrils was slightly greater in cementum than in dentine. SAXS and wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) pattern analysis allowed us to estimate the shape and size of mineral particles, revealing an increase in both thickness and length from the inner to the outer dentine. These findings confirm the presence of strong anisotropy at multiple scales within narwhal tusk tissue and suggest a three-dimensional spiral organization extending to the nanoscale. Combining 2D and 3D imaging techniques, we achieved an optimal balance between field of view, measurement time, and resolution across multiple length scales.

Combining Large Scale Facility and Laboratory Data Management within DAPHNE4NFDI

Speaker: Bishoy Hakim (contributed; FAU)

Abstract:

DAPHNE4NFDI¹ (Data from PHoton and Neutron Experiments for National Research Data Infrastructure) is a German scientific initiative focused on improving data management for photon and neutron experiments. It aims to make data more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Within DAPHNE we work towards developing a data management system, which brings together experiments at large scale facilities and the supporting experiments and simulations from laboratories. We are implementing a data management system based on NOMAD Oasis² in cooperation with FAIRmat and developing the plugin package ELNO³. It consists of converters and parsers and for the various instruments to store and share data in the NeXus⁴ format, as well as a general electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) schema with the goal of replacing paperback notebooks. A modern data management system will allow to find access and reuse data from different facilities and research groups. Sample metadata and all corresponding measurements with different methods will be available from the same catalogue. Our data management system enables data interoperability and by this fostering cooperation and interdisciplinary research.

References:

[1] <https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/index.php>, [2] <https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/nomad-oasis.html>, [3] <https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/DAPHNE4NFDI/elno>, [4] <http://www.nexusformat.org/>

Pandas for Petra

Speaker: Dawit Abiy Hailu (contributed; hereon)

Abstract:

Each Petra III experiment generates petabytes of data, including both raw and processed files. Managing data access for users and beamline scientists is increasingly challenging. Pandas for Petra (pfp) is a toolbox that, given a root folder and depth, collects all accessible files along with

their metadata and stores them as CSV, HDF5, or Parquet files. It simplifies summarizing, visualizing, and interacting with the data, and provides built-in analysis tools. For machine learning applications, the toolbox facilitates easy preparation of training datasets. The process needs to be performed only once and can then be efficiently reloaded for subsequent use.

From Raw Data to Reproducible Insights: Containerized Imaging Analysis for Synchrotron Experiments

Speaker: Vojtech Kulvait (contributed; hereon)

Abstract:

The rapid growth of synchrotron radiation imaging, from micro- to nano-tomography, has transformed research across materials science, biology, and medicine. With fourth-generation storage rings and advanced detectors, experiments routinely generate terabytes of data, creating both opportunities and challenges. While facilities must archive data efficiently, users increasingly need more than raw datasets: they require complete analytical environments—including workflows, parameters, and software—to reproduce, validate, and extend results long after beamtime. We propose a framework of portable, containerized imaging analysis workflows that travel with the data. Using Docker and Apptainer/Singularity, we encapsulate end-to-end pipelines from pre-processing to visualization, enabling re-execution across diverse platforms, from the European Open Science Cloud to institutional HPC clusters. This approach bridges the reproducibility gap between facility constraints and user needs, reducing costly data restaging while ensuring FAIR, analysis-ready contexts for future work.

Data Preprocessing Challenges in Machine Learning Applications for XAS Studies

Speaker: Athar Khodabakhsh (contributed; HZB)

Abstract:

Machine Learning (ML) approaches are increasingly adopted in material science research for the modeling and analysis of X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) data. These methods enable applications ranging from real-time spectral analysis during reaction to the prediction of structural parameters in material studies. The reliability of ML models, however, is critically dependent on the (re-)usability, interoperability, and quality of underlying XAS data. Standardized file formats, rich metadata, and high-quality spectra are essential, as model performance and reproducibility of ML models are closely tied to data quality and adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. In this study, we present data preprocessing steps of an ML pipeline and address key challenges in data cleaning and preparing training and test datasets for Anomaly Detection utilizing Autoencoders, as investigated in Work Package 4 of the ROCK-IT project, highlighting the importance of FAIR-compliant data for supporting robust, reproducible, and generalizable ML applications.

Interaction of Lysozyme with Lipid Monolayers at the Air–Water Interface

Speaker: Rabia Qamar (contributed; CAU Kiel)

Abstract:

To better understand biological processes like immune defense and membrane remodeling, it's important to study how proteins interact with membranes. In this work, we focus on lysozyme (LYZ), a positively charged antimicrobial protein. We are interested in understanding the mechanism of its interaction with a cellular membrane and how it alters the physical and chemical properties of a membrane. We performed Langmuir trough experiments to measure the surface pressure–area (π –A) isotherms of lipid monolayers composed of DPPC and POPC. These monolayers were modified with added cholesterol (15 and 30 mol%) to mimic different model membranes. Lysozyme was added to the water subphase, underneath the monolayer at low concentrations (1, 10, and 100 mg/L). Our results show that lysozyme noticeably changes the behavior of the lipid monolayers, even at very low concentrations. Langmuir isotherm measurements show significant adsorption or partial insertion of lysozyme into the lipid interface, likely driven by electrostatic interactions with polar headgroups. In combination with cholesterol, the adsorption is reduced. Interestingly, lysozyme can interact with both fluid and tightly packed membrane environments. These findings show that lysozyme is highly surface active at membrane surfaces and support its role in membrane disruption, defending against microbes, and recognizing specific lipid types. This study helps explain how even small amounts of proteins can influence membrane structure on a molecular level. In addition to the scientific results, we will also present the FAIR data handling and usage of data repositories and sample identifiers following the FAIR standards proposed by DAPHNE4NFDI.

RefXAS – an open access database of X-ray spectra

Speaker: Sebastian Paripsa (contributed; BU Wuppertal)

Abstract:

In the frame of DAPHNE4NFDI, an X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) reference database called RefXAS has been set-up where users are provided with well curated XAS reference spectra along with related metadata fields and online processing tools for visualizing the data. The developed online procedure enables users to submit a raw dataset along with its associated metadata via a dedicated website for inclusion in the database. The published data at the database can be easily linked to the raw data available at other repositories. Quality criteria formulated for the uploaded reference data at the database make users aware of the usability of the data. These quality criteria, which are unique to RefXAS, are further employed for automatic quality check of the uploaded data which is then followed by manual curation at the interface. Different XAS data formats can be uploaded to RefXAS. The output data format consists of all the important metadata provided during upload including quality criteria, curation details and bibliographic details of the data.

Diffraction line profile analysis of individual grains in a polycrystal

Speaker: Gergely Farkas (contributed; CAS)

Abstract:

Diffraction patterns from approximately 100 individual grains of a solutionized and quenched metastable β -Ti alloy were obtained using high-energy synchrotron diffraction during in-situ tensile deformation experiments. The diffraction patterns of selected grains were analyzed using an established single-crystal line profile analysis technique to assess the evolution of dislocation density on individual slip systems. The results provide a valuable complement to previously published comparisons between measured and crystal plasticity–simulated internal elastic strains (and stresses). Grains exhibiting hardening — characterized by a continual increase in grain-level stress due to increasing dislocation density — were identified, as well as a distinct population of "softening" grains in which the grain-level stress decreased with straining. Analysis using the generalized Schmid law, together with knowledge of the grain-level stress state, indicates no correlation between the most populated slip systems and the hardening/softening response of the grains.

Summary and final Discussion Round presentation of poster prizes

Time: 15:20

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